

Discussion on Tipping Point Analysis for Binary Data

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Abstract

The missing data handling is always challenging in data analysis. Especially for binary response data, we often perform tipping point analyses in clinical trials to look at what the turning points are under the assumption of missing data at random. In this paper, we discuss tipping point analyses with missing data not at random. We demonstrate our proposal regarding tipping point analyses through a simulation.

Key Words: binary data, multiple imputation, tipping point.

1. Introduction

Missing data is one of the classical issues in clinical trials and biostatistics. Statisticians have developed many different methods to handle missing data, including weighting observed values using inverse probability by Horvitz and Thompson (1952), maximum likelihood estimates by Dempster et al (1977) or imputing each missing value by Healy et al (1956), and multiple imputation by Rubin (1987). Different methods require different missingness assumptions. Rubin (1976) proposed to treat missingness indicators as random variables, which led to the definition of three main missingness assumptions: missing completely at random (MCAR), missing at random (MAR), and missing not at random (MNAR).

After the National Research Council's report on missing data was issued in 2010, there has been a shift to the prevention of the missing data. Even though prevention has been given great attention, missing data is still inevitable in any clinical trial due to different reasons. Hence, accounting for missing data is still critical in clinical trials.

When analyzing a clinical trial with missing data, usually, various sensitivity analyses need to be conducted to check if the study result is robust in handling missing data. There are many methods to account for missing data with assumptions of MCAR and MAR. In practice, many trials with missing data are analyzed under the MCAR assumption, which is generally invalid except in very special cases, or under the MAR assumption. The latter is usually considered a more sound approach than the former. Although the MAR assumption allows us to avoid specifying a model for the missingness mechanism for statistical inferences, the MAR assumption is generally not assessable as the distribution cannot be estimated from the observed data. That is, checking the assumptions of MCAR and MAR for missing data in clinical trials is challenging. In fact, many missing data patterns may not follow such assumptions.

Therefore, we need to research statistical methods to estimate the true treatment effect accurately despite having missing data under the MNAR assumption. So far, we still lack methods to handle missing data well under the MNAR assumption. In clinical trials, one method, the tipping point approach, which was defined by Yan, Lee and Li (2009), has been often used as a sensitivity analysis under MNAR assumption. This approach is also preferred by many statisticians and authorities (See Torres, 2019).

Suppose we have a clinical study with N subjects. Let $\mathbf{Y} = (y_1, \dots, y_N)$, where y_i is a value of an outcome variable for subject i . Let $\mathbf{D} = (d_1, \dots, d_N)$ be the missingness indicator, such that $d_i = 1$ for subject i with missing observation y_i , and $d_i = 0$ for subject i with non-missing observation y_i . Let $\mathbf{X} = (x_1, \dots, x_N)$ be

another set of outcome variables for all subjects and f be the probability distribution function. Hence, we simply express the three scenarios as below.

1. MCAR: $f(d|X, Y) = f(d)$, that is, the missingness is independent of X and Y .
2. MAR: $f(d|X, Y) = f(d|X)$, that is, the missingness is independent of Y .
3. MNAR: $f(d|X, Y) \neq f(d|X)$, that is, the missingness is dependent on Y .

The MNAR assumption is interpreted as both conditional probability distributions of missingness indicator being not equal. This also implies that $f(y|X, d=0) \neq f(y|X, d=1)$. That is, there are unobserved variables u which are associated with both the response and the missingness indicator, but the model for the missingness mechanism requires conditioning on the response y itself because it failed to measure u .

In this paper, we focus on binary outcomes with missing response data under the MNAR assumption.

2. Tipping Point Analysis

Assume we have two groups, “treatment” and “control,” in a clinical trial. The treatment effects of all possible combinations of the missing data values in the two groups will be estimated typically by looking at p-values and point estimates. The tipping point is a point that changes the study conclusion, that is, the statistically significant result ($p \leq 0.05$) changes into a statistically insignificant result ($p > 0.05$) at this point. If the point is considered implausible, the treatment effect will be convinced despite the missing data.

Consider a study with N subjects randomly divided into a treatment group of N_T subjects and a control group of N_C subjects with $t_i = 1$ if subject i is treated and 0 if not treated, $T = (t_1, \dots, t_N)$. Two vectors of potential outcomes $Y(t) = (y_1(t), \dots, y_N(t))$, $t \in \{0, 1\}$, indicate whether each subject would be a responder ($y_i(t) = 1$) or a non-responder ($y_i(t) = 0$) under the treatment assignment t . Let τ be the treatment effect, i.e.,

$$\tau = \left(\sum_{i=1}^N y_i(1) - \sum_{i=1}^N y_i(0) \right) / N$$

Because the treatment is randomized, the unbiased estimator of τ is

$$\hat{\tau} = \sum_{i: t_i=1} y_i / N_T - \sum_{i: t_i=0} y_i / N_C$$

Similarly, the estimator of the probability of response to missing values in each group is the sum of y_i divided by the number of missing values.

The tipping point analysis can be viewed as a special application of multiple imputation (MI) of missing data in both groups. The method is described below.

- A sequence of analyses will be performed with adjustment to artificially decrease the response rate in the treatment group and increase the response rate in the control group with a fixed and definite set of values for data imputation.
- For each combination of increasing response rate in the control group and decreasing response rate in the treatment group, multiple imputed datasets will be generated and analyzed using the Chi-squared or Cochran-Mantel-Haenszel (CMH) test. The results obtained from multiple imputed datasets will be combined using Rubin’s rule to generate statistical inference, i.e. p-value and treatment difference between the two groups.
- A “tipping point” will be identified when the result is no longer statistically significant (i.e. p-value > 0.05).

The SAS procedure MI is used to impute missing data for each shift and the SAS procedure MIANALYZE is used to combine results from all imputed datasets using Rubin’s rule.

3. Simulation

Assume one phase II 32-week (up to 4-week screening period, 24-week treatment period, and 4-week safety follow-up period), multicenter, randomized, double-blind, and placebo-controlled study to assess efficacy and safety of the study drug in subjects with moderate to severe, active rheumatoid arthritis (RA) who have inadequate response to or are intolerant to at least one biologic disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drug (bDMARD) or other. One hundred subjects are randomized to either the study drug group or the placebo group with stratification factor bDMARD or other.

The primary efficacy endpoint is the proportion of subjects who achieved ACR20 response at Week 24. An ACR20 response is defined as at least a 20% improvement in both tender joint count (TJC) and swollen joint count (SJC), and at least a 20% improvement in three of the following five criteria: patient global assessment (PGA), physician global assessment (PhGA), functional ability measure [Health Assessment Questionnaire (HAQ)], patient's assessment of pain [visual analog scale (VAS)] and C-reactive protein (CRP).

The ACR20 data are generated by Bernoulli distributions: Ber (0.60) for the study drug group and Ber (0.33) for the placebo group.

The other assumptions are as follows: Due to the investigators’ mistakes, two ineligible subjects are randomized but are asked to discontinue the treatment immediately. In addition, two subjects discontinue treatment due to safety concerns and the other six subjects discontinue treatment due to lack of efficacy per subjects’ decisions after subjects’ communication and suspecting placebo treatment in two sites. This result in 10 subjects with missing data at Week 24.

Below is the summary of the data.

Table 1: Summary of ACR20 response at Week 24

Treatment	Responder	Non-responder	Missing	Total
Placebo n (%)	12 (24.49)	31 (63.27)	6 (12.24)	49
Study drug n (%)	27 (52.94)	20 (39.22)	4 (7.84)	51

The primary analysis is to consider subjects with missing data at Week 24 as non-responders. This hypothetical strategy was applied for the primary estimand regarding the intercurrent events of treatment discontinuation. The CMH test adjusted by the stratification factor (bDMARD or other) is used for the analysis of the primary endpoint. The difference of treatment response rates between the study drug group and the placebo group is estimated as 28.44% with 95% confidence interval (9.32%, 47.55%) and p-value 0.0039. This indicates the study drug provided treatment effect for RA subjects.

Our supplemental analysis is to use observed data only for analyses, that is, only non-missing data from the 90 subjects were used. The treatment policy strategy is applied for the estimand regarding the intercurrent events of treatment discontinuation. The difference of treatment response rates between the study drug group and placebo group is estimated as 30.33% with 95% confidence interval (10.39%, 50.27%) and p-value 0.0043.

Is the primary analysis result robust? The missing data are not at random, due to different reasons. Hence, we need another analysis to check if the treatment effect for RA subjects is robust. Another issue is that more subjects with missing data were in the placebo group than the study drug group. So we need to consider different scenarios for the missing data. Hence tipping point analysis is our choice.

Table 1 shows that the observed ACR20 response rates are 24.49% and 52.29% in the placebo groups and the study drug group respectively. Hence, we perform a sequence of analyses by increasing ACR20 response rate from 24.49% to 100% for placebo subjects with missing data in the placebo group and decreasing ACR20 response rate from 52.29% to 0% for subjects with missing data in the study drug group.

For each scenario, we impute 40 datasets with monotone missing pattern through SAS procedure MI with logit link function. For each imputed dataset, we perform analyses using CMH test. Finally we combine all results from the 40 imputed datasets using Rubin's rule through SAS procedure MIANALYZE. Table 2 shows the results.

This tipping point analysis shows all possible results among these subjects with missing data. For the extreme case of almost no responders for the missing data in study drug group, tipping points happen, that is, p-values >0.05 , when almost all missing data are considered responders in the placebo group. This seems implausible. Therefore, the estimate of treatment effect of the study drug is confirmed.

We usually like to present scenarios by the number of imputed responders in each group as the intuitive interpretation is understood easily. The results are presented in Table 3.

In contrast, using Proc FREQ with the CMH test, we get the following analysis results under MAR assumption in Table 4.

Table 2: Tipping point analysis results

Deflation ratio on the odds in study drug ^a	Inflation ratio on the odds in placebo ^b (response rate difference, p-value vs placebo)							
	1	1.25	2	3	4	5	10	15
1	31.0% 0.0024	30.3% 0.0030	29.3% 0.0044	27.8% 0.0073	27.1% 0.0086	26.5% 0.0100	25.1% 0.0154	24.4% 0.0191
0.8	30.6% 0.0028	29.9% 0.0035	28.8% 0.0050	27.4% 0.0082	26.7% 0.0099	26.1% 0.0114	24.6% 0.0174	24.0% 0.0213
0.5	29.4% 0.0043	28.7% 0.0054	27.7% 0.0076	26.2% 0.0120	25.5% 0.0145	24.9% 0.0162	23.4% 0.0240	22.8% 0.0292
0.25	28.3% 0.0057	27.6% 0.0071	26.5% 0.0097	25.1% 0.0151	24.4% 0.0186	23.8% 0.0212	22.3% 0.0313	21.7% 0.0378
0.1	26.8% 0.0081	26.0% 0.0101	25.0% 0.0135	23.6% 0.0210	22.8% 0.0259	22.3% 0.0288	20.8% 0.0421	20.2% 0.0497
0.05	26.1% 0.0101	25.4% 0.0126	24.4% 0.0167	22.9% 0.0257	22.2% 0.0310	21.7% 0.0349	20.2% 0.0497	19.6% 0.0576
0.025	25.9% 0.0105	25.2% 0.0130	24.2% 0.0173	22.7% 0.0262	22.0% 0.0319	21.4% 0.0365	19.9% 0.0518	19.3% 0.0599

^a The odds of imputing missing data as responders in study drug group is decreased by the deflation ratio.

^b The odds of imputing missing data as responders in placebo group is increased by the inflation ratio.

Table 3: Tipping point analysis results presented by number of imputed responders

Number of imputed responders with missing ACR20 in study drug	Number of imputed responders with missing ACR20 in placebo (response rate difference, p-value vs placebo)						
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
0	28.5% 0.0035	26.5% 0.0084	24.5% 0.0154	22.4% 0.0282	20.7% 0.0439	19.0% 0.0650	16.8% 0.0947
1	31.4% 0.0014	29.4% 0.0041	27.4% 0.0074	25.3% 0.0143	23.6% 0.0228	21.9% 0.0374	19.7% 0.0532
2	33.6% 0.0006	31.6% 0.0021	29.6% 0.0038	27.5% 0.0081	25.8% 0.0126	24.1% 0.0221	21.9% 0.0312
3	35.1% 0.0002	33.0% 0.0008	31.1% 0.0019	29.0% 0.0042	27.3% 0.0071	25.6% 0.0129	23.4% 0.0188
4	36.1% 0.0001	34.1% 0.0004	32.2% 0.0010	30.0% 0.0024	28.4% 0.0045	26.6% 0.0078	24.4% 0.0126

Table 4: Tipping point analysis results with MAR assumption

Number of imputed responders with missing ACR20 in study drug	Number of imputed responders with missing ACR20 in placebo (response rate difference, p-value vs placebo)						
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
0	28.5% 0.0037	26.4% 0.0073	24.4% 0.0137	22.3% 0.0244	20.3% 0.0415	18.2% 0.0675	16.2% 0.1052
1	30.4% 0.0020	28.4% 0.0041	26.3% 0.0080	24.3% 0.0147	22.2% 0.0258	20.2% 0.0433	18.2% 0.0698
2	32.4% 0.0011	30.3% 0.0022	28.3% 0.0045	26.3% 0.0085	24.2% 0.0155	22.2% 0.0269	20.1% 0.0449
3	34.3% 0.0005	32.3% 0.0012	30.3% 0.0024	28.2% 0.0048	26.2% 0.0090	24.1% 0.0162	22.1% 0.0279
4	36.3% 0.0003	34.3% 0.0006	32.2% 0.0013	30.2% 0.0026	28.1% 0.0051	26.1% 0.0094	24.0% 0.0167

Tables 3 and 4 confirm that only in the extreme case of almost no responders for the missing data in study drug group, tipping points happen when almost all missing data are considered as responders in placebo group.

4. Discussion

Missing data cannot be avoided in all clinical trials. Due to expensive trial costs, almost all sample sizes in all clinical trials are just enough for the test power. Hence, it is critical to apply robust methods to confirm the primary efficacy analysis results. Certainly, we can apply different imputation methods, such as last observation carried-forward and worst observation carried-forward, for the missing data according to different diseases.

However, no perfect imputation methods can mimic the true data. Hence, we still need to monitor each study to avoid any missing data. The high quality of study conduction is the result of all efforts from different functions. For large studies or long-term studies, it is possible to have missing data at the data base lock. The tipping point approach is widely used because of the simulation algorithm and easy implementation. Many drug applications were also requested to perform tipping point analyses. Therefore, it is a reasonable choice for handling the missing data in clinical trials. In addition, tipping point approach may be robust no matter if we use MAR or MNAR assumption.

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